

An assessment of strategic Leadership and organisational resilience of Indigenous Construction firms in Rivers State

Ezugu, Virgilus Chukwudi^{1*}, Dr. Mercy F. Ajienka², Hettey, Hubert Daniel (PhD)³ and Oshi, Joseph E. O. (PhD)⁴

¹University of Port Harcourt Business School (UPBS). Port Harcourt

²Management Department FMS, University of Port Harcourt. Nigeria

^{3,4}Management Department, University of Port Harcourt, Nigeria

Received 10, November, 2023, Accepted 12, December 2023, Published 15, June 2024

This study investigated the relationship between strategic leadership and the resilience of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State, focusing on adaptive capacity and innovativeness. The study employs a positivist philosophical framework, utilizing a questionnaire to collect data from 62 top-level management staff of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State. The hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Findings reveal a significant positive relationship between strategic leadership and both adaptive capacity and innovativeness. In conclusion, the study contributes to closing a gap in the literature, emphasizing the crucial role of strategic leadership in enhancing the resilience of indigenous construction firms. Recommendations include prioritizing strategic leadership development and promoting a culture of innovation within these organizations. The insights provided have practical implications for industry practitioners, policymakers, and future research endeavors in the Nigerian construction sector.

Keywords: Strategic leadership, Organizational Resilience, Adaptive Capacity, Innovativeness

INTRODUCTION

The construction sector is very crucial to every nation's social and economic development. Apart from the sector's potential of employment generation, various activities undertaken in the sector are very germane to fostering effective linkages and enhancing as well as sustaining economic development (Adeagbo, 2014). It contributes significantly to both Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Gross Fixed Capital Formation (GFCF) of all nations (Tunji-Olayeni et al., 2017). The country's construction industry has an estimated market size of between US\$26.9 billion and US\$40.3 billion, accounting for 9% of GDP (Construct Africa, 2022). However, indigenous construction firms (ICFs) in Nigeria struggle to survive in a harsh business environment characterized by

intense competition and relatively low profit margin due to factors such as poor work quality, cost overrun frequent delays, increased rework and low productivity (Tunji-Olayeni et al., 2017), which impacts negatively on their resilience. Due to a fast changing corporate environment, economic crises, environmental disasters, and increasing competitiveness, modern businesses are confronted with a myriad of environmental strain. Thus, organisational resilience has become one of the most crucial foundations for managing complexity, unpredictability, crises, and pressure and competitive battles (Al Balushi, 2020).

Leaders are crucial to the formulation, implementation and control of strategy for any organization (Miriti, 2021), they make sense of and give meaning to environmental turbulence ambiguity and provide a vision and road map that allows an organization to evolve and innovate. Accordingly, it can be hypothesized that strategic

*Corresponding author's e-mail: virgilservicesltd@yahoo.com

leadership predicts organisational resilience. On this premise, it is assumed that strategic leadership could predict organizational resilience. Strategic leadership refers to a set of unique capabilities of anticipating envisioning, maintaining flexibility, thinking in a strategic way, and empowering employees to generate innovative ideas that lead to high performance (Ireland & Hitt, 1999).

While many researchers have looked at what makes an organisation resilient, no one seems to have examined the impact that strategic leadership has on that resilience, especially in the indigenous construction sector of Nigeria, particularly Rivers State. Therefore, to fill this gap, this study intends to determine the nature of the relationship between strategic leadership and resilience of indigenous constructions firms in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Several factors affect the resilience of indigenous construction companies in Nigeria. For instance, the current high level of inflation impacts the level of working capital requirements for construction companies, making it difficult for indigenous construction firms to manage their finances effectively (Ugochukwu & Onyekwena, 2014). Also, delays in interim payments affect the cash flow of construction companies, leading to financial difficulties and reduced resilience (Ugochukwu & Onyekwena, 2014). More so, multiple taxation, taxation at source and deduction of retention which is synonymous with the industry in Nigeria, impact the financial performance of indigenous construction companies (Ugochukwu & Onyekwena, 2014).

Furthermore, most indigenous construction firms do not have the financial muscle and strength to tender for high yielding construction projects in the State. Buttressing this, Obodo et al. (2021) identified certain project risk factors such as task uncertainty, job difficulty, contract status, project consultant, economic conditions, resource availability, and building legislation and government regulation, all of which significantly influence indigenous contractors' tender for construction projects. They also noted that the influx of foreign construction firms into the country has heightened the level of competition in the industry, which also impacts the resilience of indigenous construction companies.

In addition, a major challenge most indigenous companies face has to do with their competencies and project delivery. Due to their size, experience, and influx of foreign construction companies and harsh business environment, most indigenous firms find it difficult to cope (Ogunde et al., 2016). To improve the resilience of indigenous construction companies in Nigeria, it is essential for these firms to address these factors and adapt to the changing construction landscape. It is against this backdrop that this study investigated the role of strategic leadership in enhancing the resilience of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to determine the nature of the relationship between strategic leadership and organizational resilience of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Examine the nature of the relationship between strategic leadership and adaptive capacity of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State.
- ii. Investigate the nature of the relationship between strategic leadership and innovation of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State.

Research Questions

To achieve the aim and objectives of the study, the following research questions are posed:

- i. What is the nature of the relationship between strategic leadership and adaptive capacity of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State?
- ii. How does strategic leadership relate to innovation of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State?

Research Hypotheses

As a guide to the rest of the study, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between strategic leadership and adaptive capacity of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between strategic leadership and innovation of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Strategic Leadership

Boal and Hooijberg (2001) define it as the ability to create and maintain absorbent and adaptive capabilities and to perceive environmental opportunities via shrewd managerial decision making. According to Bass (2007), it consists of the company's top executives who come up with the overarching plans for gathering and allocating the company's resources. Rowe and Nejad (2009) describe it as the distribution of similar ideals and a clear vision to employees, as well as the ability to make decisions with few organisational limits. Strategic leaders include CEOs, board members, and other high-ranking managers (Simsek et al., 2018), and they are accountable for making difficult choices that will have long-lasting consequences for the company and its

stakeholders (O'Shannassy, 2016). According to Davies and Davies (2004), successful strategic leaders have the strategic orientation skills required to put their strategies into action, despite their frequent dissatisfaction with their existing learning and experience levels.

Organizational Resilience

Previous research has proven a connection between organisational resilience and being well-prepared for and responsive to change. Planned resilience and adaptive resilience are congruent with this, as argued by Barasa et al. (2018). Zwane and Kanyangale (2019) also agree that beneficial adaptation requires careful planning, and that planned resilience is a facilitator of adaptive resilience. Negative adaptation might result from a lack of preparation. To cope with environmental changes, businesses need to practise both anticipatory and non-anticipatory planning (Duchek, 2020).

Adaptive Capacity

Although some consider adaptive capacity to be synonymous with response capacity (IPCC, 2019), others view it as a more general concept (Gallop, 2006), given that certain adaptations can affect a system's sensitivity or exposure to particular perturbations, or even boost its resilience (Walker et al., 2004). According to Zhu et al. (2017), a company's performance increases when its leaders are able to adapt to new circumstances. Owner-managers may use their adaptive ability to modify internal tactics like change management and resilience, and to better connect with external entities like customers, organisational cultures, and rivals (Ali et al., 2017). Ability of individuals, communities, organisations, governments, and other players to adjust to the current and future consequences of global climate change is a contentious but useful definition (Gallop, 2006).

Innovativeness

As stated by Isichei et al. (2020), "firm innovativeness is seen as a fundamental pillar for building a competitive edge over other firms operating in the same industry and business environment" due to the fact that it enables the firm to capitalise on consumers' ever-evolving tastes and desires by catering to niche markets. Products, services, processes, and even bureaucratic innovations all fall under the umbrella term "innovation". While product innovation seeks to create new goods and services to satisfy consumers' wants and needs (Damanpour & Gopalakrishnan, 2001), process innovation aims to enhance manufacturing and distribution by introducing novel approaches to these previously established processes. According to the findings of this study (Tsai & Yang, 2013), innovativeness is correlated with improved company success. Ng et al. (2012) state that

innovativeness is a means through which new goods and procedures may be integrated to boost a company's bottom line.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

Upper Echelons Theory

The seminal work of Hambrick and Mason, "Why do organisations function as they do? It is generally agreed that (1984) is the starting point for this idea. They moved attention on the power and influence of a company's top executives, such as the CEO and CFO. The idea is based on the belief that the knowledge, talent, and experience of a company's key senior individuals have an impact on its results (Hambrick & Mason, 1984). They said that CEOs face new challenges every day and that the strategic choices they make are highly influenced by their own personalities. Thus, the policies and procedures of an organisation mirror the attitudes and worldviews of its important members (Carpenter et al., 2004). Strategic leadership and organisational resilience research will benefit from this notion.

Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT)

Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT) (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000; Yu et al., 2019) posits that in order for a business to maintain a competitive edge over time, it must be able to rapidly adapt to new circumstances by developing and deploying new capabilities or reallocating existing ones. This idea is an outgrowth of the Resource Base View (RBV) hypothesis, which posits that an organization's prosperity may be analysed in terms of the variety of its precious, rare, and necessary assets (Liu et al., 2016). RBV is unable to provide an adequate assessment of capabilities when disruptions occur in unexpected scenarios, in contrast to DCT, which prepares resources and capabilities in response to changes in each state. When an enterprise is resilient, it is able to anticipate and adapt to change while facing challenges and unpredictability in its external environment, a concept captured by the dynamic capacity theory.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Kaehler et al. (2014) examined the relationship between adaptive capability and strategic orientations in the organizational context. In order to achieve this, an empirical study was carried out in a Brazilian agency for maritime services, via a survey of 160 employees. The results show a positive correlation between all of the strategic orientation variables and their respective adaptive capability.

That is, the findings show that the company's strategic orientations affect its adaptive capability, and also

suggest that the stronger the respondents' perception of the company's dynamic capability, the higher its organizational adaptive capability in its market of operation. Mwangi et al. (2022) reviewed existing conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature on adaptive capability and organizational performance with a view to highlighting the knowledge gaps suitable to form basis for future research work. Existing empirical literature on the relationship between adaptive capability and organizational performance have been conducted in developed countries using small samples hence diversity of contextual variables. The review also revealed key indicators of organizational performance as one of the outcomes of adaptive capability in organizations. From the reviewed literature, a set of relationships for the dimension of adaptive capability and organizational performance were modeled as a guide for future research work in the field of strategic management.

Fagerdal et al. (2022) explored and describe how leaders enable adaptive capacity in hospital teams. The article reports from a multiple embedded case study in two Norwegian hospitals. A case was defined as one hospital containing four different types of teams in a hospital setting. Data collection used triangulation of observation and interviews with leaders, followed by a qualitative content analysis. It was revealed that leaders contribute in several ways to enhance their teams' adaptive capacity. The study identified four key enablers;

- (1) building sufficient competence in the teams;
- (2) balancing workload, risk, and staff needs;
- (3) relational leadership;
- (4) emphasising situational understanding and awareness through timely and relevant information.

Thus it was concluded that team leaders are key actors in everyday healthcare systems and facilitate organisational resilience by supporting adaptive capacity in hospital teams. Kılıç (2022) focused on understanding the relationship between strategic leadership and innovative performance. To test the theoretical model quantitative method was applied.

This study was conducted on 345 white collar employees working in the manufacturing sector in Istanbul, Turkey. For the research, data collection method questionnaire application was implemented during May, June, July, and August in 2021. The survey response rate is 77%. As a result of the factor and correlation analysis there is positive and significant relationship between strategic leadership and innovative performance.

According to correlation analysis transformational leadership ($r = 0.712$) and political leadership ($r = 0.703$) sub-dimensions have a higher correlation with innovative performance, managerial ($r = 0.498$) and ethical leadership ($r = 0.543$) have a positive relation with innovative performance as well. According to ANOVA test

results, it was also found that there are differences in the perception of strategic leadership based on age level. Followers at 20 - 30 ages have higher strategic leadership perceptions than others. Maziti et al. (2018) sought to investigate the relationship amongst determinants that affect small business performance in South Africa. The determinants under focus included: a) strategic leadership, b) competitive advantage, and c) innovation performance. A positivist philosophy relying on a quantitative approach using a survey design was adopted for the study. A sample of 275 small business owners representing their firms filled a survey using established measures.

Findings show a relationship to exist between strategic leadership with innovation performance and competitive advantage. Further, innovation performance was found to be related with quests for competitive advantage. Based on this, management practices for contemporary society are made that provide a basis in which forecasting and planning techniques can be used for the purpose of competitive intelligence. Elenkov et al. (2005) investigated the relationship of strategic leadership behaviors with executive innovation influence and the moderating effects of top management team (TMT)'s tenure heterogeneity and social culture on that relationship. Using survey data from six countries comprising three social cultures, strategic leadership behaviors were found to have a strong positive relationship with executive influence on both product-market and administrative innovations.

In addition, TMT tenure heterogeneity moderated the relationship of strategic leadership behaviors with executive innovation influence for both types of innovation, while social culture moderated that relationship only in the case of administrative innovation.

METHODOLOGY

The research is motivated by the positivist philosophical framework. Primary sources, in the form of a questionnaire, was used to gather information for this study. Fifteen (15) statement items made up the questionnaire. The predictor variable is strategic leadership it was measured using items adapted from the works of Greene and Brown (2009) and Zappalà and Toscano (2020). The criterion variable is organisational resilience, and its proxies are adaptive capacity and innovativeness. It was measured using an instrument adapted from the works of Akgün et al. (2012) and Pallister and Foxall (1998).

The study participants comprised of top level management staff of indigenous construction companies in Rivers State. A total of sixty-two (62) top level management staff of indigenous construction companies in Rivers State, responded to the questionnaire. Responses obtained via the administration of the

Table 1. Frequencies and Percentages of Demographics.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Gender				
Male	62	100.0	100.0	100.0
Marital Status				
Married	62	100.0	100.0	100.0
Age				
30 - 40	5	8.1	8.1	8.1
41 - 50	18	29.0	29.0	37.1
50 years and above	39	62.9	62.9	100.0
Total	62	100.0	100.0	
Highest Educational Qualification				
Bsc or Equivalent	8	12.9	12.9	12.9
Masters or Equivalent	31	50.0	50.0	62.9
Doctorate Degree	23	37.1	37.1	100.0
Total	62	100.0	100.0	
Number of years in the organization				
Less than 5 years	3	4.8	4.8	4.8
6 - 10 years	7	11.3	11.3	16.1
10 years and above	52	83.9	83.9	100.0
Total	62	100.0	100.0	

Table 2: Test of Relationship between Strategic Leadership and Adaptive Capacity.

		Strategic Leadership	Adaptive Capacity
Strategic Leadership	Pearson Correlation	1	.670**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	62	62
Adaptive Capacity	Pearson Correlation	.670**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	62	62

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 3: Test of Relationship between Strategic Leadership and Innovativeness.

		Strategic Leadership	Innovativeness
Strategic Leadership	Pearson Correlation	1	.793**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	62	62
Innovativeness	Pearson Correlation	.793**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	62	62

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

questionnaire were coded and the hypotheses developed in line with the aim and objectives of the study were tested using Pearson product Moment Correlation Coefficient.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results and Analysis

Demographic Analysis

Table 4.1 shows the demographic characteristics of the

respondents. All the respondents in this study were male and they are all married. Also, majority of the participants reported to be 50 years and above – 57 (i.e. 62.9%), followed by those between 41 and 50 years of age (18, 29.0%). In addition, 50% of the participants had Master's Degree or its equivalent as their highest educational qualification, followed by 37.1% of them who reported to have Doctorate Degrees; the remaining respondents also had reasonable degree of education haven reported to have a BSc or its equivalent. Lastly, 83.9% of the respondents have been with their organization for more than 10 years.

In conclusion, the demographic characteristics of the

study participants indicate that the indigenous construction industry in Rivers State is predominantly male, possibly due to the nature of work in this sector. All the respondents were married, aged 50 and above, and held advanced degrees, suggesting a cognitively mature and experienced sample. The choice of such a sample is relevant for understanding the dynamics of strategic leadership and organizational resilience in the challenging context of construction industry.

Test of Hypotheses

In this section of the study, the tests on the hypotheses (bivariate), is presented. The section addresses the relationship between strategic leadership and the measures of organizational resilience (adaptive capacity and innovativeness). The hypothetical relationships between these variables are considered to be non-directional, as such each hypothesis is structured as two-tailed and focuses on the significance of the relationship (positive or negative).

The result for the relationship between relational strategic leadership and adaptive capacity is presented in table 4.2. The result reveals that the relationship between strategic leadership and adaptive capacity is positive and significant at $r = .670$ and $p = 0.000$. Consequently, the null hypotheses is not supported. In other words, the study empirically supports that there is a significant relationship between strategic leadership and adaptive capacity.

The result for the relationship between relational strategic leadership and innovativeness is presented in table 4.3. The result reveals that the relationship between strategic leadership and innovativeness is positive and significant at $r = .793$ and $p = 0.000$. Consequently, the null hypotheses is not supported. In other words, the study empirically supports that there is a significant relationship between strategic leadership and innovativeness.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between Strategic Leadership and Adaptive Capacity

The study conducted by Kaehler et al. (2014) supports the identified significant relationship between strategic leadership and adaptive capacity. The study, based on a survey of 160 employees in a Brazilian agency for maritime services, reveals a positive correlation between strategic orientation variables and adaptive capability. The findings suggest that a company's strategic orientations influence its adaptive capability. Furthermore, Mwangi et al. (2022) contribute to this understanding by emphasizing the importance of adaptive capability in organizational performance. Their

review of existing literature highlights key indicators of organizational performance as outcomes of adaptive capability. Therefore, the positive relationship observed in the study aligns with the broader perspective presented in the literature, reinforcing the crucial role of strategic leadership in fostering adaptive capacity.

Relationship between Strategic Leadership and Innovativeness

The study by Kılıç (2022) directly supports the identified significant relationship between strategic leadership and innovativeness. Kılıç (2022) focused on the manufacturing sector in Istanbul, Turkey, conducting a quantitative study on 345 white-collar employees. The results indicate a positive and significant relationship between strategic leadership and innovative performance. Notably, specific sub-dimensions of strategic leadership, such as transformational and political leadership, exhibit higher correlations with innovative performance. The findings resonate with Maziti et al.'s (2018) investigation into small business performance in South Africa, where a positive relationship between strategic leadership and innovation performance is established. Together, these studies provide a robust foundation for understanding the link between strategic leadership and organizational innovativeness.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Therefore, based on the evidence presented, it can be concluded that strategic leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping the adaptive capacity and innovativeness of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State. This study contributes to the existing body of knowledge by filling a gap in the literature, particularly in the context of the indigenous construction sector in Nigeria. The implications of these findings underscore the importance of strategic leadership in enhancing the resilience of organizations facing challenges in the construction industry, providing valuable insights for practitioners, policymakers, and researchers alike. Based on this, it is recommended that the management of indigenous construction firms in Rivers State should:

- i. Prioritize the development of strategic leadership capabilities within their leadership teams. To achieve this, organizations should invest in leadership training programs that focus on skills such as anticipation, envisioning, flexibility, and strategic thinking. These programs should not only enhance the theoretical understanding of strategic leadership but also provide practical tools for leaders to navigate the complex and dynamic construction business environment.
- ii. Actively promote a culture of innovation within

their organizations. This involves encouraging leaders to adopt transformational and political leadership styles that have been found to correlate positively with innovativeness. To achieve this, organizations can establish innovation-focused initiatives, such as idea generation platforms, cross-functional collaboration, and recognition programs for innovative contributions

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